

The Impact Failure Prediction of FRP Pressure Vessels Using Finite Element Method

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SUMMARY

The target of this study is a fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) pressure vessel which is used as a fuel storage tank in a fuel cell (FC) car. In this paper, an FE model of an FRP pressure vessel was validated with impact tests, and it was found that it is possible to predict the failure of the pressure vessels using that.

Keywords: Finite Element Analysis, Failure Analysis, FRP, Pressure Vessel

CONTENTS

Introduction

FC cars use FRP pressure vessels to store hydrogen fuel. It is very important to ensure safety in the case of car accidents. Therefore it is necessary to use impact tests and computer analyses during development to estimate the safety performance. FE analysis is very effective in terms of reliability and cost.

In this study, the authors propose a method of the failure prediction using FE analyses of FRP pressure vessels; and furthermore validate the model with impact tests.

The drop impact test

A full size FRP pressure vessel was pressurized with hydraulic pressure and was impacted by a drop weight. The difference in failure mode was clarified for a range of different inner pressures, impact velocities, and weights. (Fig. 1)

FE model of pressure vessels

FE analyses were conducted using LS-DYNA Ver. 971. The model of the pressure vessel, including FRP failure rules, was made by the authors^[1] and is shown in Fig. 2.

Comparison of the experiments and the simulation

The load curves, displacement curves, load-displacement curves, and failure modes of the experiments and simulations are compared. Some of the experimental failure modes did not agree with the predictions of the simulation, but the failure boundaries generally agreed.

The failure prediction of FRP pressure vessels

Once validated, the model can be used to predict the failure of the vessel for additional test conditions, making it easy to design the storage strength.

Fig. 1 Test conditions and results

Fig. 2 FE model of the pressure vessel

Reference

1. T. Kaneko et al. Damage analysis of composite vessels under impact loading using the finite element method. Society for the advancement materials and process engineering. In press.